

Awareness and Use of NTR-MEDNET Digital Library Consortium E-Resources among the Postgraduate Students of Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS), Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh

Srinivas Sonteni

Research Scholar

Dept. of Library & Information Science

Central University of Tamil Nadu,

Thiruvarur-610005

E-mail: sontenivasu@gmail.com

Murali Taddi

Asst. Professor

Dept. of Library & Information Science

Central University of Tamil Nadu

Thiruvarur-610005

E-mail: taddimurali@gamil.com

Abstract

The study's main intention is to explore the awareness and use of NTR-MEDNET digital library consortium e-resources among the postgraduate students of Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS), Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh. The investigator adopted a survey method. The questionnaire was designed to fulfill the objectives of the study and 160 questionnaires were distributed to the postgraduate students. 152 useful questionnaires were tabulated, analyzed and SPSS software was used for the simple percentage. The study findings show that the main problems found are login issues. Furthermore, the most useful database is the clinical key. The study also revealed that students are using NTR-MEDNET resources for academic/teaching purposes. The study recommended that RIMS, kadapa should take some more steps for increasing computer nodes at digital libraries and library professionals should inform the all level of students for up to date information on consortium resources. Besides the post graduate medical students need to get training/awareness programs regularly for an effective use of NTR-MEDNET e-resources

Keywords: Awareness and Use, Andhra Pradesh, Consortium, Digital Library, Electronic Resources, Postgraduate Students.

0. Introduction

Libraries are knowledge hubs for disseminating the exact and useful information to the users whenever necessary anywhere any time without hurdle and delay. Today Information and Communication Technology is growing in every field, especially in the medical and health profession. E-resources are playing a major role in education, research and academic activities. E-resources include e-databases, e-books, e-journals, e-animations, e-slides, e-reports, Web-OPAC and e-dictionaries/encyclopedias. E-resources are highly helpful to health professionals for education and research activities. In academic scenarios E-resources are supported to hence the professional skills in the medical education as well as in research. Dr. NTR University of health science, Andhra Pradesh provides NTR-MEDNET digital library consortium E-resources to all the affiliated health science colleges in Andhra Pradesh. The consortium e-resources are highly useful to the medical postgraduate students for their academic purposes. The present study is to examine the awareness and use of E-resources provided by the NTR-MEDNET digital library consortium to the postgraduate students of Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Medical Sciences (RIMS) Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh.

1. Background of NTR-MEDNET Digital Library Consortium

Dr. NTR University of Health Sciences (NTRUHS) Andhra Pradesh started the NTR-MEDNET digital library consortium in the year 2008. The consortium's main objective is to provide a wide range of E-Resources to all affiliated health science colleges in Andhra Pradesh. All the affiliated health science institutes should take institutional membership. It was started with the goal to improve the quality of health science education and enhance the research in the field of health institutes in Andhra Pradesh. The consortium provided world famous health sciences databases, apart from e-journals, case studies, continuous health education, e-animations, e-slides, e-medical reports, training programs to the faculty-students-library professionals and online webinars.

2 Study Objectives

- To determine the awareness on NTR-MEDNET digital library consortium e-resources by the post graduate medical students.
- To examine the use pattern of electronic resources provided by the NTR-MEDNET Digital Library Consortium.
- To evaluate the purpose of using digital library consortium electronic resources by the postgraduate medical students.
- To find out the satisfaction level of e-resources provided by the consortium.
- To evaluate the barriers during the using of e-resources by the students.
- To describe the need of user education/training programs for enhance the optimum utilization of e-resources by the medical postgraduate students.

3 Literature Review

Chanchinmawia, and Verma (2016) study found that 66% of respondents are aware on the UGC-INFONET digital library consortium and 49% of the student's consortium e-resources are very useful. The study found that 70% of the respondents used consortium e-resources for personal updates in their study on UGC-INFONET digital library consortium. Chauhan, Suresh K and others (2011) survey found that the less usage of UGC-INFONET facilities among the research scholars and faculty members is the main problem that lacks awareness on electronic resources. The study was conducted on UGC-INFONET digital library in India. Francis (2012) discussed his study on use of consortium e-resources in Kerala Agriculture University. The study results show that the using online based information resources, CD-ROM databases 100%, e-journals 69.29% and e-database 25.71% respectively. The study also found that the majority of the students 63.12% knew the required searching skills for accessing consortium bases e-resources provided by the university. Bhatt (2010) study revealed that the UGC-INFONET digital library consortium is a major useful consortium for providing access to a wide range of electronic resources for all universities and colleges in India. The study also revealed that 60% of respondents are using e-resources for the up to date purpose and the low access speed is the main hurdle during the access of consortium e-resources. Garg (2014) conducted a study on use of UGC-INFONET digital library consortium at Kurukshetra and Maharshi Dyanand University. The study results show that the use of consortium e-resources for the purpose of article publishing and keeping up to date information on the subject and 69% respondents require regular training programs on user education and orientation programs. Deepak Kumar and Sharma (2020) study revealed that majority of the (63.89%) respondents were using e-resources for completion of assignments and seminars provided by the UGC-INFONET consortium and they were potentially satisfied with consortium e-journals. Selvamani and Thavamani (2017) discussed their paper on use of ERMED consortium facilities. The findings show that the majority of the respondents are satisfied with consortium e-resources and majority of the respondents are using consortium resources for teaching purpose.

4 Methodology

The investigator used the survey method for data collection for this study. The population of the present investigation is confined to postgraduate students of RIMS, Kadapa, Andhra Pradesh. 160 Postgraduate students were randomly selected from each of the clinical, Para-clinical and non-clinical departments and restructured questionnaires were administered to the selected students. Collected questionnaires were carefully checked and unfilled questionnaire were omitted. Finally, 152 questionnaires were used for this research. The study mainly focuses on the post graduate students only. The final data was tabulated and analyzed for the study. MS-Excel and SPSS software was used of the purpose of simple percentages

5 Data Analysis and Findings

Table 1

Demographic Details of the Respondents

Gender	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage %
Male	94	61.8
Female	58	38.2
Total	152	100
Study Course	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage %
MD	75	49.3
MS	77	50.6
Total	152	100
Study Year	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage %
PG-1 st Year	42	27.6
PG-2 nd Year	51	33.5
PG-3 rd Year	59	38.9
Total	152	100

From the **table 1** above, of the 152 participants, 97 (61.8%) were male, while 58 (38.2) were female. The study course of the participants shows that 75 (49.3%) MD participants, 77 (50.6%) were MS. The year wise participants are 59 (38.9%) highest from the third year, 42 (27.6%) lowest from final year students.

Table 2

Do you aware about NTR-MEDNET consortium E-Resources

Awareness	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage %
Not at all aware	6	3.94
Slightly aware	37	24.35
Moderately aware	45	29.60
Very much aware	35	23.03
Extremely aware	29	19.08
Total	152	100

Table2: shows the results regarding awareness on consortium resources, majority of the respondents 45 (29.60%) were moderately aware, this is followed by 37(24.35%) were slightly aware, 35 (23.03%) very much aware, 29 (19.08%) extremely aware and low 6 (3.94%) respondents were not at all aware on consortiums resources. It was indicated that the majority of the medical postgraduate students aware on consortium e-resources.

Table 3

Frequency of use of NTR-MEDNET digital library consortium e-resources

Frequency	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage %
Daily	48	31.5
Weekly	29	19.1
Fortnightly	24	15.8
Monthly	27	17.8

Occasionally	17	11.2
Never	7	4.6
Total	152	100

Table 3 results show about 152 respondents; majority of the students 48 (31.5%) frequency of e-resources used daily, 29 (19.1%) 'Weekly', 24 (15.8%) 'Fortnightly', 27 (17.8%) 'Monthly', 17 (11.2) 'Occasionally' and 7 (4.6%) is least frequency used of e-resources

Table 4

Most useful databases for academic/teaching/teaching/research purpose

Useful Databases	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage %
DyanMed Plus	13	8.6
EBSCO Medical Collection	17	11.2
EBSCO	25	16.4
EBSCO Sports Medicine Collection	7	4.6
EBSCO Alternative Medicine	6	3.9
ProQuest	20	13.2
Clinical Key	43	28.3
Clinical Student	11	7.2
ISABEL EBSCO Database	10	6.5
Total	152	100

Table 4: indicate that most useful database for academic/research/teaching purposes to offer NTR-MEDNET e-resources. The most useful database is clinical key 43 (28.2%), the second highest useful database is EBSCO 25 (16.4%), ProQuest 20 (13.2%), EBSCO medical collection 17 (11.2%), DyanMed Plus 13% (8.6%) Clinical student 11 (7.2%), ISABEL EBSCO database 10% (6.5%), EBSCO sports medicine 7 (4.6%) and EBSCO alternative medicine 6 (3.9%) was used by the students for their academic/research/teaching purposes.

Table 5

Purpose of using NTR-MEDNET e-resources

Purpose of using	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage %
Articles/Book Publication	32	21.1
Seminar/Conference/Workshop	33	21.7
Dissertation/Project	38	25.0
Teaching/Academic	49	32.2
Total	152	100

Table5: results show that the majority of the respondents 49 (32.2%) were used NTR-MEDNET e resources for their academic/teaching purposes. Further, 32 (21.1%) students used e-resources for article/book publication. 33(21.7%) students opted for seminar/conference/workshop purposes. 38 (25.0%) respondents used for dissertation and academic purposes.

Table 6

Reason for using NTR-MEDNET e-resources

Reason	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage%
Easy to Search/Retrieval	14	9.2
Advanced search facility	31	20.4
Up-to-date Knowledge	38	25
Easy to download	27	17.8
Relevant to subject	28	18.4
Time Saving	14	9.2
Total	152	100

Table 6: The findings show that majority of the students 38 (25%) were using NTR-MEDNET for up-to-date knowledge, 14 (9.2%) were used for easy to search/retrieval, 31 (20.4%) were opted to advanced search facility, 27 (17.8%) students were reason for using e-resources for easy to download, 28 (18.4%) were using e-resources for relevant to subject and 14 (9.2%) were using electronic resources for the reason of time saving.

Table 7

Satisfaction Level of using NTR-MEDNET e-resources

Satisfaction	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage%
Satisfied	72	47.4
Highly Satisfied	35	23
Average	30	19.7
Below Average	12	7.9
Poor	3	2
Total	152	100

Respondents were asked to level of satisfaction of using NTR-MEDNET consortium e-resources and results are showed that in **table 7**: majority of the respondents 72 (47.4%) were satisfied followed by 35 (23 %) were highly satisfactory, 30 (19.7%) were average, 12 (7.9%) were said that below average satisfaction and very low 3 (2%) were said that poor satisfaction about e-resources offered by NTR-MEDNET. It was indicated that the majority of students are satisfied with using the consortium resources.

Table 8

Problems faced during the access of NTR-MEDNET e-resources

Problems	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage%
Publishers/Vendors Restrictions	28	18.4
Low Internet Bandwidth	27	17.8
Login Problems	32	21.1
Irrelevant information	21	13.8
Delay of current issue	21	13.8
Full text not download	23	15.1
Total	152	100

The respondents were requested to indicate the barriers faced during the access of electronic resources, **table 8**: shows that the most common barrier was the login problem to retrieve the needed information cited by 32 (21.1%) of respondents. Next were publishers/vendors retractions mentioned by 28 (18.4%) respondents, followed by 21 (13.8%) irrelevant information, 21 (13.8%) respondents were faced delay of current issue and 23 (15.1%) respondents were faced problem by full text not downloaded.

Table 9

User education/training programs is require for the optimum usage of NTR-MEDNET e-resources

Options	No of Students (N=152)	Percentage%
Agree	47	30.9
Strongly Agree	61	40.1
Disagree	20	13.2
Strongly Disagree	10	6.6
Can't Say	14	9.2
Total	152	100

The question asked to the respondent's the user education/training program is require to optimum utilization of consortium e-resources. Table 9: clearly indicated that the majority of the respondents 61 (40.1%) were agreed. Next 47 (30.9%) respondents said they strongly agree for needed user education/training programs. 20 (13.2%) opted to disagree, 10 (6.6%) respondents were said to strongly disagree and 14 (9.2%) students said their opinion can't be said. Ultimately it was clear that regular user training/awareness programs are mandatory for optimum utilization of e-resources.

Major Findings

- The study found that the majority of the medical postgraduate students 45 (29.60%) moderately aware about NTR-MEDNET consortium E-Resources.
- The tabulated results show that majority of the respondents 48 (31.5%) frequency uses of e-resources by daily and never used e-resources by respondents are 7 (4.6%).
- The survey revealed that the most useful database is clinical key 43 (28.2%) cited by students and lowest 6 (3.9%) EBSCO alternative medicine database was used by the students for their academic/research/teaching purpose.
- Results show that the majority of the students 49 (32.2%) were used NTR-MEDNET e resources for their academic/teaching purposes and lowest 32 (21.1%) students were used e-resources for article/book publication.
- The survey results show that high percentage of respondents 72 (47.4%) were overall satisfied with NTR-MEDNET consortium e-resources and very low 3 (2%) students said that poor satisfaction on e-resources.
- It was observed that login problem 32 (21.1%) is a major barrier to retrieve the needed information from e-resources and 21 (13.8%) respondents were faced by delay of current issue and irrelevant information both equally.
- The studies revealed that majority of the respondents 61(40.1%) were agreed that user education/awareness program is mandatory for optimum usage of NTR-MEDNET e-resources and least 10 (6.6%) students opted can't say regarding user education programs.

Major Recommendations

- After careful review of the finding, the investigator would like to suggest the following recommendations.
- The University should conduct user training /awareness programs for library professionals and postgraduate students regularly offline and online both equally
- Library professionals play a key role to inform the students about the e-resources on a regular basis.
- Library professionals should remain the consortium e-resources through e-mail and WhatsApp group services.
- Students should visit the library regularly for up to date services provided by the digital library.
- The health university should add the high quality medical databases in NTR-MEDNET consortium e-resources. If students are properly used these e- rescuers definitely improve their professional and research activities.
- Medical college faculty member should be aware of up-to-date knowledge on NTR-MEDNET digital library consortium resources and frequently inform first year to final year postgraduate medical students regarding the usefulness of these resources for their research and academic activities.
- NTR-MEDNET consortium regularly monitoring the usage statistics from all the affiliated colleges and give instructions to the faculty members, students and library professional for the better usage of consortium e-resources.

6 Conclusion

The finding shows that electronic information resources are more useful to the postgraduate students of Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Medical Science, Andhra Pradesh. Dr. NTR University of Health Sciences was provided a wide range of NTR-MEDNET digital library consortium electronic resources to all the affiliated health sciences institutions. The present study findings revealed that the majority of the students are aware of NTR-MEDNET e-resources. It is a positive sign from the student's side for interested on consortium e-resources. Institutions shall take the necessary steps for the optimum utilization of health science literature via NTR-MEDNET digital consortium resources. The consortium main objective is to high utilization of electronic resources by the medical students. The consortium was spending a huge budget for subscription of International databases and purchasing medical literature for the purpose student's benefits. Unfortunately, the students were not using the consortium resources properly. Medical students should pay interest on e-resources and utilize the services provided by the NTR-MEDNET consortium.

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